

ASSESSMENT OF GOODS-MATERIAL RESERVES AND FINANCIAL INFORMATION ABOUT THEM DISCLOSURE FEATURES IN THE REPORT

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6526755>

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Annotation: *Inventory effectively organizes the activities of business entities plays an important role in the cost of the product. Inventory is correct valuation allows the formation of reliable accounting information. In the article the nature of inventories, their valuation and financing according to international standards the procedure for disclosure is described in the report.*

Key words: *inventories, valuation, cost, net selling price, international standard, work in progress, finished goods, goods*

Modernization of the economy developed in the conditions of business entities in the general system of indicators reflecting the efficiency of production activities the cost of the product plays a key role. Because reducing the cost of the product increase in profit of the business entity, leads to the creation of additional opportunities to expand its activities. In this regard President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev In his report, he noted the following: "The first is how effective the reforms are target programs that show that they are providing implementation efficiency. These include

The following economic and financial indicators of the development of industry and other sectors can be cited: the state of production capacity, costs and cost. reduction, localization and profitability level, unconditional product competitiveness increase »

Indeed, providing the population with quality and affordable products is crucial in increasing the competitiveness of our economy in the world market rational use of materials and resources, inefficient cost savings and product cost reduction plays an important role. The economy any farm in the conditions of modernization inventory at its disposal proper organization of the reserve account and increase the efficiency of their use will be required.

Commodity inventories - normal for later sale held in the process of operation and available in the production process, as well as product manufacturing, work in the process of performing or providing services or administrative and socio-cultural functions material used to make assets.

Inventories in the process of formulating accounting policies in accounting in estimating write-offs for groups different methods can be used. This they incur additional costs in the process re - inserting, removing stocks discard and stockpile in the area where they are located the environment that occurs when shopping includes valuation obligations for recovery.

Performed using a commodity inventory to the essence of the increased economic operation if attention is paid to it, then it is reflected in the purchase, use and write-off is provided. Paying attention to the methods of their receipt in the accounting of inventories should.

It is necessary to make sure that the indicators, expressions and numerical values in all documents examined in the course of business activities are interrelated. Documents verification and analysis not only in form but also in content, as well as primary arithmetic reflected in accounting documents checking the accuracy of calculations need For this purpose, scientific research has been conducted.

Normative costs of raw materials and supplies, taking into account labor, efficiency and productivity takes They are regularly analyzed, taking into account current conditions as necessary case will be reconsidered. Retail pricing method used to estimate inventories in retail. The unit value of the reserve is this reserve

The selling price of the unit belongs to the gross profit is determined by reducing the percentage. The amount of interest used their value in determining them first will be reduced below the selling price.

Inventories at the end of the reporting year reflected in the balance sheet and explanatory note, based on the use of inventory valuation methods, at the determined value.

Financial statements should highlight:

- used to estimate reserves accounting policies, including the method used to calculate cost;
- total carrying amount of reserves and the type of users used by this enterprise reserve value on;
- minus the cost of selling inventories accounted for at current value the resulting book value;

- recognized as an expense during the reporting period the amount of reserves received;

- recognized as an expense during the reporting period any reduction in the reserves received

- caused the depreciation of reserves circumstances or events;

- supply to fulfill obligations as the value of the collateral

Full disclosure of inventory information in the financial statements is accounting accuracy and transparency of information provides.

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